

Critical points for diversity across academic career trajectories

Krishma Labib, María de los Ángeles Crespo López & Rita Santos

Factors contributing in favor of DEI

Addressed by R&R policies

Factors contributing against DEI

Structural problems and bias

Stages: school

- Structural inequalities in school education
- Bias against first generation students and minority backgrounds
 - *Example 1: schools ask for parents' level of education, which influences decisions made regarding education profiles and access to higher education*
 - *Example 2: students from minority ethnic backgrounds are less likely to be given support and access to higher education*

[Go back to infographic](#)

Bias, barriers, access

Stages: Bachelor to PhD

- Bias is present in marketing strategies for recruitment of students
- Tuition fees are a barrier for higher education for those from lower socio-economic backgrounds
- Lack of support for work-life-study balance challenges
- Inequitable institutional access to contacts
- Poor supervisor fit and lack of supervisor support
- Lack of diversity and understanding about DEI among student advisors

[Go back to infographic](#)

Mobility expectations, ageism, visas and little support

Stage: PhD to Postdoc

- Expectations of PhD candidates and postdocs of temporarily relocating to conduct research abroad
 - *This is exacerbated by the fact that most funding schemes immediately post-PhD are mobility schemes (e.g. Rubicon, Marie-Curie)*
- Ageism negatively impacts older researchers from pursuing PhDs and postdocs
- Dealing with visa issues and residence permits tied to employment adds to precarity
- Lack of support present for those starting a family; instead, this is seen as a 'problem' to deal with

[Go back to infographic](#)

Lack of support and narrow view of diversity

Stage: Assistant to Full Professor

- Lack of support available for life events, care-taking responsibilities and illness
- Career progression strongly influenced by informal networks and departmental decisions.
 - *This is a problem because most marginalized researchers will not have access to the same networks and possibilities as those with more privileges.*
- DEI reduced to 'gender equality' promotion, focusing only on gender binary

[Go back to infographic](#)

COIs and bias in recruitment and promotion

Stage: PhD to Full Professor

- Biases in hiring and promotion procedures
- Lack of awareness and training in biases
- Conflicts of Interest in hiring and promotion committees
 - *Example 1: Supervisors/close colleagues/fellow department members of candidates not excluded from committees*

[Go back to infographic](#)

Discrimination and barriers

All stages

- Discrimination on the basis of sex, gender, race, ethnicity, religious background, ability, neurodivergence, socio-economic background, LGBTQI+ identity
 - *Example: women, particularly with minority backgrounds, receive more disrespectful and negative student evaluation results, while these can be used for determining promotions*
- Language barriers for non-Dutch speakers
- Cultural barriers for those belonging to minority cultural backgrounds
 - *Example: a 'borrel' culture focused on bonding at work via drinking activities is exclusive to researchers that feel uncomfortable with drinking due to cultural, religious or health reasons*

[Go back to infographic](#)

Precurity

Stage: Postdoc

Unstable short-term job contracts disproportionately disadvantage those who are already most marginalized, such as those from lower socio-economic backgrounds, researchers with care-taking responsibilities, disabilities, and non-European nationalities

[Go back to infographic](#)

Hiring and recruitment bias

Stage: Master to Postdoc

- Bias against those with flexible academic plans, i.e. bias towards those pursuing non-traditional academic trajectories
- Evaluation of CVs without taking into account differences caused by life events and identity
 - *Example: It is unfair to judge students on low number of secondments and conference attendance, if they struggle to obtain visas to travel abroad due to inequities in how nationalities are treated in international travel*

[Go back to infographic](#)

Flexibility, accommodations, and special funds

Stage: School to PhD

- Flexibility in attendance rules when necessary, e.g. due to students' care-taking responsibilities or disabilities
- Support and accommodations available for students' personal circumstances, e.g. related to health issues, disabilities and neurodivergence
- Special funds available for first generation students

[Go back to infographic](#)

Accounting for differences in CVs

Stage: Master to Postdoc

Upon recruitment and promotion, HR could provide information to committees on background information which is important to consider when evaluating CVs. It does not make sense to judge all CVs on Dutch standards if candidates have studied or worked previously in a different context with different expectations.

[Go back to infographic](#)

Inclusive leadership and broad understanding of diversity

All stages

- Leaders who are trained in and committed to DEI
- Accessible buildings
- Support for networks representing different groups at the university
- A broad understanding of diversity that takes into account different types of identities and their intersections
 - *Examples: gender (understood as a spectrum), race, ethnicity, religious background, nationality, age, socio-economic background, ability, neurodivergence, LGBTQI identity, care-taking responsibilities*

[Go back to infographic](#)

Tenure

Stages: from Assistant Professor

Tenure provides stability for researchers, which helps those who achieve it to be able to continue in academia despite potential life challenges or situations they might encounter

[Go back to infographic](#)

Unbiased hiring and special provisions

Stage: PhD to Full Professor

- Hiring and promotion committees that are trained in implicit biases, DEI and fair procedures
- Guidance and involvement of HR in hiring and promotion procedures
- Funding made available to help researchers re-integrate after leave, e.g. due to illness or care-taking responsibilities
- Adequate provisions given to researchers with different needs, e.g. related to accessing prayer rooms, lactation rooms, etc.

[Go back to infographic](#)